
AN ALTERNATIVE FRAMEWORK: ASSIMILATING NANCY FRASER'S THEORY WITH AXEL HONNETH'S CONCEPT OF JUSTICE

BY PRISHA GOEL¹

ABSTRACT

Nancy Fraser's theories on redistribution and recognition are highly influential in the current discourse of social justice due to the comprehensive and complex nature of intersectionality and justice. Although Fraser's framework provides insightful information, it does not provide a thorough understanding of interpersonal dynamics. In contrast, this is provided by Axel Honneth's conception of Justice that incorporates social spheres like love, legal rights, and respect. In this paper, I aim to provide an alternative framework that incorporates important elements of both Fraser's and Honneth's concepts. By synthesizing both concepts, we would be provided with a better understanding and a holistic perspective of social justice. I argue that addressing the dual perspectives of material conditions of oppression and symbolic aspects of misrecognition is essential.

Keywords: Redistribution, Recognition, Social Justice, Substantive dualism

I. INTRODUCTION

The concept of identity is dynamic and closely linked to recognition and redistribution, two fundamental concepts that are essential for social justice. Nancy Fraser in her paper titled 'Social Justice in the Age of Identity Politics: redistribution, recognition, participation' has proposed a framework that explores the relationship between these concepts. In this paper, I will examine whether identity, redistribution, and recognition are interconnected or can be studied separately. I will also examine the debates that surround redistribution and recognition in the context of social justice and how intersectionality plays a role in the dynamic. Further, I

¹ Author is a student at O.P Jindal Global University

intend to question if substantive dualism is enough and analyse an alternative perspective of perspectival dualism.

II. UNRAVELLING THE DILEMMA: RECOGNITION VS REDISTRIBUTION OR BOTH?

Recognition aims to understand and value the diverse customs, practices, and behaviours of individuals is fundamental for various groups to participate in society fully. According to Fraser, recognition is a matter of justice as opposing Charles Taylor and Axel Honneth who argue that it's about self-realization. Deprivation of the status of a complete social partner due to institutionalized patterns of cultural value, as well as being devalued in the conscious attitudes of others leads to misrecognition. She recognizes misrecognition as a barrier to social inclusion, regardless of the internal experiences of the oppressed. Fraser emphasizes recognizing cultural differences without stereotyping is important. She advocates multiculturalism that goes beyond mere tolerance of groups and promotes equal recognition of diverse identities. For instance, the caste system in India has led to a lack of social recognition and cultural affirmation of the lower castes. They face widespread stigma, prejudice, and exclusion with the prevailing social norms devaluing and diminishing their identities. Alternatively, Redistributive justice seeks to create a fair and equitable society by distributing resources and benefits among all members of society, rectifying the imbalances caused due to economic disparities. Various marginalized groups face economic disparities that are tied to their social identity. Historically, the caste system has led to deeply entrenched economic differences, due to which lower casts face exclusion from resources and opportunities. They have been relegated to menial work, lack of education and opportunities.

Existing theories on distributive justice fail to address issues of recognition. While some recognize the importance of status, their approach relies on a reductive economic and legalistic understanding of status. This perspective assumes that a just distribution of resources and rights is sufficient to prevent misrecognition. While theories about recognition also prove insufficient to address redistribution problems. Theorists recognize the importance of economic equality and fairness, but they often involve a reductive culturalist view of distribution. It assumes that changing cultural orders is adequate to prevent maldistribution rooted in economic inequalities. This binary division forces us to choose between class politics or identity politics, social democracy, or multiculturalism and, creates separation between cultural and social politics. Therefore, a theory of justice that goes beyond cultural value patterns or

economic structures alone and considers both recognition and distribution adequately is needed. Fraser argues that social justice can be achieved by combining redistribution and recognition. By integrating these two concepts, we can create a comprehensive framework that accommodates both social equality and cultural differences. Identity, redistribution, and recognition are inherently connected and cannot exist in isolation. Thus, it is important to embrace the emancipatory aspects of both redistribution and recognition to achieve social justice.

III. ALTERNATIVE FRAMEWORK: PERSPECTIVAL DUALISM-

Creating a framework that addresses recognition and distribution is challenging due to the complex relationship between class, status, maldistribution, and misrecognition. The goal is to acknowledge these issues practically, considering the differences and interactions between class and status. Fraser criticises the concept of Dualism where redistribution and recognition are seen as distinct spheres of justice as it overlooks the interdependence of economy and culture. Instead, Fraser argues for examining the economic underpinnings of cultural practices as well as the cultural underpinnings of economic processes. This approach allows us to view every practice as both economic and cultural, assessing them from both redistributive and recognition standpoints without diminishing one another. Fraser proposes perspectival dualism as an alternative to substantive dualism. It allows for the analysis of social practices from both distributive and recognition perspectives, evaluating their impact on economic and cultural conditions for participatory parity.

Example:

Caste discrimination denies cultural recognition and causes economic exploitation. Dalit's access to opportunities and resources is restricted due to the economic marginalisation that leads to a continuation of the cycle of poverty and exclusion from equal participation in society. Systemic injustices are maintained because of the stigma and the social exclusion associated with lower castes in the country. This ultimately leads to a diminished sense of self-worth and dignity. Thus, an approach that deals with both the spheres of cultural recognition and economic disparities is required. Redistribution-based policies like affirmative action and land reforms can reduce economic disparities by providing equal access to resources, jobs, education, etc. It's imperative to introduce initiatives that counter caste-based discrimination such as grassroots movements to demand social recognition and support representation.

IV. ANALYSIS

Nancy Fraser's framework allows a detailed analysis of the intertwined and intersectional nature of social inequalities and varied forms of injustice experienced by marginalized communities. A systematic examination of the multifaceted nature of the present injustices can be done through the distinction made between redistribution and recognition. While both Honneth and Fraser emphasize the importance of recognition, Honneth's theory lays more emphasis on aspects like psychological and emotional dimensions.² According to him, social injustices arise when individuals or groups are excluded from these spheres since it leads to a diminished sense of self, leading to alienation, humiliation and disrespect. The main difference is that Honneth recognizes the psychological and emotional dimensions of recognition while Fraser gives a comprehensive analysis of the structural and intersectional dynamics of injustice.³

According to me, the psychological and emotional dimensions of justice can't be ignored since they have a fundamental impact on the individual self-worth and dignity. Experiences of different groups are inherently different and therefore subjective. The focus on the subjective aspect of recognition resonates with me since emotional well-being and relationships are essential to the understanding of social justice.

I would propose changes in the framework of Nancy Fraser in a way that incorporates the psychological and emotional aspects of justice. Expanding on Honneth's distinction between the areas of love, rights, and solidarity, Fraser's framework could include the acknowledgment of these areas in her structure.⁴ Cultural recognition could include love emphasizing the importance of interpersonal relationships. Her framework already emphasizes legal recognition. Her analysis could highlight the significance of legal institutions in safeguarding individuals from discrimination and injustice by including Honneth's concept of rights. Solidarity stands for acknowledgment, recognizing mutual support and acknowledgment, and its role can be associated with social struggles. By integrating, Honneth's theory into Fraser's

². Roland Pada, AXEL HONNETH'S SOCIAL PHILOSOPHY OF RECOGNITION, <https://www.cambridgescholars.com/resources/pdfs/978-1-5275-0310-6-sample.pdf> (last visited May 10, 2024).

³ Ibid

⁴ Ibid

framework, the intersectionality aspect can be addressed effectively, since the interconnectedness of love, rights, and solidarity can be considered along with race, gender, class, etc. Both also advocate for the role that social movements and struggles place in achieving social justice. Integrating their concepts into a unified framework, would lead to a better understanding of these movements and lead to birth of creative strategies to achieve justice. Fraser's framework has been influential in addressing issues of injustice and inequality. However, given the multifaceted nature of these issues, the framework needs to be more comprehensive. So, it's imperative to involve the emotional and psychological aspects, address intersectionality, and broaden the concept of recognition. Moreover, we need to emphasize the role of recognition in redistribution and differentiate forms of recognition. By doing so, we can create a more just and equitable society that addresses the needs of diverse communities and individuals.

